

An Analysis and Study of Consumer Behaviour and its Concerning Issues

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ABSTRACT

Consumer behaviour is the study of how individual customers, groups or organizations select, buy, use, and dispose ideas, goods, and services to satisfy their needs and wants. It refers to the actions of the consumers in the marketplace and the underlying motives for those actions. This paper describe about the Consumer behaviour and its concerning issues like its nature, relationship with digitalization and existing studies and literature etc.

Key Words: *Consumer, behaviour, digital, paradigm etc*

1. INTRODUCTION

Consumer behaviour is the investigation of how individual clients, gatherings or associations select, purchase, use, and arrange thoughts, merchandise, and administrations to fulfill their needs and needs. It alludes to the activities of the consumers in the commercial center and the basic thought processes in those activities.^{1,24}

Advertisers expect that by understanding what makes the consumers purchase specific merchandise and enterprises, they will probably decide—which items are required in the commercial center, which are outdated, and how best to show the products to the consumers. Consumers' shopping habits have changed over the past decade. The use of digital technology to research, browse and purchase has gone from segment-specific or sporadic to mainstream. This has resulted in an undeniable and nonreversible shift in the retail landscape². Unremitting technological changes are significantly altering the behavior of the consumers across the globe. Pervasive, inexpensive, compatible, easy and advanced technology has urged customers to

become smarter, informed, connected, updated, and empowered.³ Consumers have become “prosumers” whereby consumers are not only at the receiving end but are also getting actively involved in co-creating, customizing and passionately promoting the marketing content in socially connected era. Marketers have also understood and appreciated the change brought by technology that has been registering its stark presence among the consumers. This change is affecting the lives of both the marketers and consumers in concrete ways.⁴ The greatest example of change is the „internet“ that has significantly altered the ways of communication, sharing and finding information and doing business.⁵

2. Digital Technologies:

The tremendous growth of the internet and particularly the “World Wide Web” or WWW which made consumers and firms participating in a global online marketplace which eventually urged marketers to try and deal with the innovative ways of marketing in computer mediated environments. The steady and swift integration of internet with myriad devices and proliferation of digital technologies in recent times has further fuelled the change.^{6,7} This interactive medium of today has crossed the borders of a conventional computer's screen and has embraced many digital devices namely mobile phones, smart phones, tablets, digital outdoors and digital TV. This revolution in digital technologies has urged companies to restructure the marketing practices, especially in communication to engage successfully with past, present and potential customers.^{8,9} Digital technologies, particularly the internet, has transformed the every aspect of business namely the business communication, branding, product management, supply chain management, buying and selling and customer relationship management to name a few. Technology's usage in business has accounted for

reducing the numerous business costs along with offering competitive advantage.¹⁰

3. Literature Review:

The target of non-positivist research endeavour is to accomplish a superior comprehension of consumer behavior with no particular plan to impact consumer forms. Then again, results of positivist research are coordinated toward propelling the objectives of showcasing practice. By recognizing the paradigmatic moves inside the field, this article means to distinguish various floods of idea that could control future consumer examine. Consumer is the investigation "of the procedures included when people or gatherings select, buy, use, or discard items, administrations, thoughts, or encounters to fulfill needs and wants" (Solomon 1995, 7).

In the promoting setting, the expression "consumer" alludes not exclusively to the demonstration of procurement itself, yet in addition to examples of total purchasing which incorporate pre-buy and post-buy exercises. Pre-buy action may comprise of the developing attention to a need or need, and a quest for and assessment of data about the items and brands that may fulfill it. Post-buy exercises incorporate the assessment of the acquired thing being used and the decrease of any tension which goes with the buy of costly and inconsistently purchased things. Each of these has suggestions for buy and repurchase and they are manageable in contrasting degrees to advertiser impact (Foxall 1987).¹¹

Engel, et al. (1986, 5) characterize consumer behavior as "those demonstrations of people straightforwardly engaged with acquiring, utilizing, and discarding financial products and ventures, including the choice procedures that go before and decide these demonstrations". Straightforward perception gives restricted knowledge into the mind boggling nature of consumer decision and specialists have progressively looked for the more refined ideas and techniques for examination given by behavioral sciences so as to comprehend, anticipate, and perhaps control consumer behavior all the more adequately. Brain science, social brain research, and human science are the orders most generally utilized in this undertaking which has turned into a considerable scholastic industry in its own right.¹² So as to build up a structure for the investigation of consumer behavior it is useful to start by considering the advancement of the field of consumer inquire about and the various ideal models of idea that have affected the order (Marsden and

Littler, 1998). Standards in consumer research can be extensively delegated a lot of central suspicions that scientists make about what they are examining and how they study it (Kuhn, 1962).

As depicted beneath, a lot of measurements can be distinguished in the writing, which can be utilized to describe and separate the different points of view on consumer behavior. Consumer behavior itself developed as an unmistakable field of concentrate during the 1960s. A noteworthy synergist impact in its rise was the development of the Association for Consumer Research in 1969. Enrollment presently surpasses 1700 (www.acrweb.org), and the developing development of the field is reflected in its yearly gathering procedures, entitled *Advances in Consumer Research*.^{13,14} The writing has developed strongly, with the *Journal of Consumer Research* (first distributed in 1974) remaining as a head source. All the more as of late, the *Journal of Consumer Psychology* was propelled in 1992.¹⁵

4. Consumer behaviour Characteristics:

4.1 Constant change: Consumer behavior isn't static. It experiences a change over some stretch of time contingent upon the idea of items. For instance, kids incline toward bright and extravagant footwear, yet as they grow up as youngsters and youthful grown-ups, they favor stylish footwear, and as moderately aged and senior natives they lean toward increasingly calm footwear. The adjustment in purchasing behavior may occur because of a few different considers, for example, increment salary level, training level and advertising factors.^{16,17}

4.2 consumer to consumer Variation: All consumers don't carry on in a similar way. Different consumers act in an unexpected way. The distinctions in consumer behavior are because of individual factors, for example, the nature of the consumers, way of life and culture. For instance, a few consumers are technoholics. They go on a shopping and spend too far in the red. They obtain cash from companions, relatives, banks, and on occasion even receive deceptive intends to spend on shopping of development innovations.¹⁸ Be that as it may, there are different consumers who, regardless of having surplus cash, don't go notwithstanding for the standard buys and stay away from use and buy of development advances.¹⁹

4.3 Region to region Variation: The consumer behavior changes crosswise over states, locales and nations. For instance, the behavior of the urban consumers is not quite the same as that of the provincial consumers. A decent number of rustic consumers are moderate in their purchasing behaviors. The rich provincial consumers may reconsider to spend on extravagances regardless of having adequate assets, while the urban consumers may even take bank advances to purchase extravagance things, for example, autos and family unit machines.^{20,21} The consumer behavior may likewise shifts over the states, locales and nations. It might vary contingent upon the childhood, ways of life and level of advancement.

4.4 product to product Variation: Consumer behavior is distinctive for various items. There are a few consumers who may purchase greater amount of specific things and exceptionally low or no amount of different things. For instance, young people may spend vigorously on items, for example, PDAs and marked wears for pretender request, however may not spend on general and scholastic perusing.²² A moderately aged individual may spend less on dress, however may put cash in reserve funds, protection plans, benefits plans, etc.²³

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